

Interdisciplinary Ontology & Aesthetics Characteristic via Interactive Animation

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Abstract

Interactive animation art represents a dynamic and interdisciplinary form of expression that merges traditional animation with interactive media, fostering user engagement and participation. This research explores the ontological components of interactive animation—Instrument, Display, and Socializing—and its creation through a research-creation methodology that integrates theoretical, technical, and creative processes. Utilizing Flash in the early 2000s to Unity 3D and WebGL formats today, this medium has evolved to embody scientific aesthetics, such as quantum principles, emphasizing uncertainty and emergence. The interactive questionnaire exemplifies this interdisciplinary, demonstrating the principle that “no interaction occurs without interference.” This research underscores the importance of interference as a core characteristic of interactive animation, providing a framework for understanding its unique capacity for engagement. The findings redefine the boundaries of art and technology, suggesting interactive animation’s potential to offer deeply immersive and personalized experiences.

Keywords: interactive animation, scientific aesthetics, research-creation, interactive questionnaire, media interference.

Ontología interdisciplinaria y características estéticas a través de la animación interactiva

Resumen

El arte de la animación interactiva representa una forma de expresión dinámica e interdisciplinaria que fusiona la animación tradicional con los medios interactivos, fomentando la participación y el compromiso del usuario. Esta investigación explora los componentes ontológicos de la animación interactiva (instrumento, visualización y socialización) y su creación a través de una metodología de investigación-creación que integra procesos teóricos, técnicos y creativos. Este medio, que utiliza Flash a principios de la década de 2000 y los formatos Unity 3D y WebGL en la actualidad, ha evolucionado para incorporar la estética científica, como los principios cuánticos, enfatizando la incertidumbre y la emergencia. El cuestionario interactivo ejemplifica esta interdisciplinariedad, demostrando el principio de que “no se produce interacción sin interferencia”. Esta investigación subraya la importancia de la interferencia como característica central de la animación interactiva, proporcionando un marco para comprender su capacidad única de participación. Los hallazgos redefinen los límites del arte y la tecnología, lo que sugiere el potencial de la animación interactiva para ofrecer experiencias profundamente inmersivas y personalizadas.

Palabras clave: animación interactiva, estética científica, investigación-creación, cuestionario interactivo, interferencia de los medios.

Introduction

Interactive animation is a dynamic form of art that involves either abstract or concrete imagery, created to facilitate interactive participation rather than mere recording. This medium emphasizes creation and user engagement, transcending traditional boundaries with its interdisciplinary nature. It enables personalized control and artistic exploration beyond the competitiveness found in conventional games. The ontology of interactive animation art encompasses three primary components: Instrument, Display, and Socializing.

Research-Creation of Interactive Animation

Research-Creation of Interactive Animation is an interdisciplinary field of research that combines traditional animation techniques with interactive media. This area of research concerns the use of animation and interactive media to create interactive experiences for users. This research area aims to explore new ways of art expression and academic instrument through animation and interactive media.

Methodology Statement

Research-creation for Interactive Animation Art combines creative processes, experimental aesthetics, and art as integral parts of research studies (Chapman & Sawchuk, 2012, p. 5). This methodology has been adopted in digital humanities and social sciences (Khoury, 2017, p. 29) and allows for research data to be generated from art projects and experiences (Chapman & Sawchuk, 2012, p. 16). In addition, research-creation is suitable for answering ‘How’ and ‘Why’ questions and can offer a critical view

of video games, leading to a grounded theory based on the authors' experience and art/game history (Lelièvre, 2018, p. 9). Interactive animation art is a form of art that combines creative expression with technology (Sadati & Mitchell, 2021, p. 1). Research-creation is a promising way to discover innovative results (Khoury, 2017, p. 28) and can offer academic legitimacy and objectivity to artist-researchers in their quest for knowledge (Lelièvre, 2018, p. 16). This methodology is a critically motivated approach to practice (Westecott, 2020, p. 14), and provides creative iteration and advancement in the field (Khoury, 2017, p. 260).

Experimental creations and theoretical experiences

As web design evolved, some technologies have faded away. The rise of smart mobile devices has significantly increased mobile web browsing. Flash Player, once dominant for web animations, declined due to Apple's restrictions on iPhones and iPads, and Adobe's decision to stop supporting Flash Player for Android in 2012. JavaScript started in 1995, regained prominence due to its cross-platform capabilities. The journey in interactive animation creation began in 2006 with Flash, used for an undergraduate project at Sichuan Fine Arts Institute. Flash's 2D animation and interaction coding were crucial for early interactive animations. In the 2006 project 'Dream of Life: Thought Fragments', ActionScript was used to control the playback of an experimental short film through interactive hardware connections showed in Figure 1.

Figure 1. 'Dream of Life: Thought Fragments' (Interactive Animation by Flash), Zhao Jie, 2006.

Flash was not only an animation tool but also a creative medium for early online interactive media art. Since the late 1990s, artists like Chinese flasher Wang Bo (Pi San) and Dutch visual artist Han Hoogerbrugge used Flash for artistic creation. Wang Bo created notable works such as "Serial Dream" and "Play Me," showcasing the unique charm of Flash. Hoogerbrugge, introduced in the book "Animation Unlimited," transitioned from traditional media to Flash, creating interactive works like "Flow," "Hotel," and "Nails," which vividly depicted the era's spiritual connotations. Inspired by ancient literature and modern life, the project "Journey to the Modern" reimagined characters from "Journey to the West" as modern office workers. Monk Tang became an accountant, Pigsy a boss, Monk Sha a courier, and Monkey King a rebellious clerk. This blend of classical character traits with contemporary settings created new character images. The project utilized Unity and WebGL to explore interactive 3D animation, preparing for the creation of an interactive questionnaire in the PhD research showed in Figure 2.

Figure 2. 'Journey to the Modern' (Interactive Animation by Unity 3D), Zhao Jie, 2016.

In 2016, a special study tour on 'Virtual Reality and Network Technology in New Media Art' with an opportunities to visit many new media art institutions and studios in Germany, including the Multimedia and Virtual Interactive Design Centre (MMVR) of the Halle Academy of Art and Design, the Cultural Integrated Education centre of Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT, <http://www.zak.kit.edu>), the Intelligent Sensing and Actuation System Research Centre (ISAS, <http://isas.uka.de/>), and the Karlsruhe centre for Art and Media (ZKM). Conducted professional discussions and exchanges with German new media creators and technical experts.

Based on the methodology of the Research-Creation, the artistic practice and exchange of interactive animation during the study visit in Germany, two academic monographs were published namely 'Interactive Animation Design: Zbrush + Autodesk + Unity + Kinect + Arduino 3D Somatosensory Technology Integration' (2016), and 'New Media Crossover Interaction Design' (2017). The practice of combining creation with theoretical research has strengthened and deepened the understanding of the 'Research-Creation' methodology showed in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Monographs based on methodological 'Research-Creation'.

Research creation as a methodology used by artist-researchers in academia has been used both in connection with traditional art forms and digital arts, e.g. in the research of games (Lelièvre, 2018, p. 2). This interactive questionnaire, created using Unity3D and published in WebGL format, supplements traditional survey methods by incorporating gamified interactive animations to reflect academic analysis and objective behavioural data. A domain name is registered, and a virtual host is set up to send data collected in Unity3D to a MySQL database on the virtual server. Participants are randomly assigned to one of three game-like levels: Level 1 features a thinker with a changing head, Level 2 has flip panels that switch unpredictably, and Level 3 includes entangled digital sculptures that respond to clicks. The questionnaire's scientific aesthetics, inspired by quantum concepts like uncertainty, randomness, and entanglement, enhance engagement showed in Figure 4.

Figure 4. 'Quantum Art Gallery' (Interactive Questionnaire), Zhao Jie, 2024.

A/B testing with over 600 participants uses the 'LagTimer' variable to measure the duration of presence in specific scenarios, with positive values indicating extended stays in area A and negative values in area B. Preliminary results show a positive correlation between TimerA and Lag Time, aligning with the questionnaire's design expectations. The characteristic of interactive animation as 'No interaction occurs without interference' (Zhao, Dalal, Abu Bakar, *et al.*, 2024, p. 142; Zhao, Dalal, Bakar, *et al.*, 2024, p. 20).

Conclusions

Interactive animation, characterized by the intersection of scientific aesthetics such as quantum principles (uncertainty, randomness, superposition, entanglement, and emergence), emphasizes the principle of 'No interaction without interference'. This principle provides a framework for understanding interactive animation's unique characteristics and potential. By embracing interference, artists and designers can create more engaging experiences. Interactive animation differs from traditional 2D/3D animations and games through its non-linear narrative, personalized content, and user participation, prioritizing artistic expression over competitiveness. The convergence of Instrument, Display, and Socializing integrates digital creativity and human interaction, enhancing contemporary art practices and offering immersive experiences that redefine modern digital art.

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